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A Creative Folio

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The Abduction of Princess Lawanen (Role Play version)

Scene 1: The Abduction

Princess Lawanen swings between the two mighty trees in the Kingdom of Bembaran. On the other hand, King Dimasangkay, the King of Kadaraan, is using his telescope to find the Princess he has vowed to marry. He drifts alongside the sea of Bembaran.

Dimasangkay: What is happening! A thick cloud covers the kingdom of Bembaran. I can't see anything!

Turning on the other side, the beauty beyond compare, the cause of his grief and sleepless nights, was trapped in the eyepiece of his telescope.

Dimasangkay: What shall I do now? Shall I call the fairy spirit to abduct her?

King Dimasangkay commands the fairy spirit to come as wind and abduct the Princess Lawanen to board his sail. In a few minutes, the Princess found herself on the ship of King Dimasangkay.

Princess Lawanen: Why am I here? If the King is truly wise, he will send me back to my kingdom. Obviously, you have me abducted away from my home!

The King is about to step near the Princess when all of a sudden, the wall of fire appears between them. Since he couldn't coerce the Princess, he decided to banish her from his mind, then befriended her at the right time. He commands his sailors to row faster all the way to the kingdom of Kadaraan.

Scene 2: The King's Plan

The news spread around the kingdom of Bembaran that the Princess was abducted. The King sounded the gong to inform other kingdoms to prepare for war.

People of Bembaran: The Princess is nowhere to be found. The Princess is missing!

Wise men: Maybe, this is the fulfillment written in the prophecy, the book of omens, that the King of Kadaraan will abduct the Princess.

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King of Bembaran: We have to form and assemble our armies in the land of the Flower Kingdom, the place of Minalang, before we attack the kingdom of Kadaraan.

Their ship is loaded with cannons, and they sail along the endless sea.

Scene 3: The Two Ships

Upon the vast sea, the boat of Rinayong, mighty King of Bembaran, crossed paths with the vessel of Kalipapa Da'ayaw, the valiant Mabaning.

Captain Lomayon: Who are these sailors? Why are they making fun of in the middle of the sea? Are they aware that all kingdoms are subject to a search for finding the missing Princess, and the King has forbidden making fun of the sea?

The captain is about to throw cannons at the other boat when he recognizes the voice of Prince Mabaning, the fiancée of Princess Lawanen.

Captain Lomayon: Prince Mabaning, are you aware that the Princess beyond compare is missing? The King of Kadaraan abducted him!

The tears of Prince Mabaning are about to fall. He is expecting to celebrate with the Princess the victory he achieved after surviving the battle from which he came. Upon hearing the news, he decided to join them in searching for the missing Princess. The two boats move in one direction. When the two boats are about to reach Kadaraan, a decisive blow of wind accompanied by strikes of lightning sets the two boats apart. The captain of Rinayong was worried about Prince Mabaning when all of a sudden, he saw him standing within their boats.

Captain Lomayon: I was worried about you. You are now safe with us.

Prince Mabaning: My ardent request to you is to send me to that shore. I will find other ways to find the Princess.

Even though Captain Lomayon disagrees with the safety of the prince at stake on that shore, he can't refuse his ardent request.

Scene 4: The Baroraw Forest

To conceal his noble blood, Prince Mabaning took the form of a Madem, the ancient hermit of the mountains.

Madem: Hey friend, where are you going?

Gypsies: We are emissaries of Minalang. We are actually searching for the missing Princess. The rumor is that the Flower Kingdom is teeming with people of Bembaran preparing to invade Kadaraan.

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Madem: I am also an emissary of Minalang. I am also tasked to search for the missing Princess. I am having trouble finding the Baroraw Forest. May I go with you?

Gypsies: Sure!

The prince thanked his new friends. He has now reached the Baroraw Forest. He decided to take rest for a while under the shade of a tree when the fairy Princess Anonen Pangadapen, the Princess of Kaugan, approached the sleeping prince.

Princess Anonen: What makes you tired? You seem very lonely and feel uneasy.

Prince Mabaning: The Princess of Bembaran is missing. I have gone this far, but still she's nowhere to be found.

Princess Anonen: The Princess of Bembaran is in the palace tower of Sagorongan-a-Ragat. However, I advise you not to come there, for the kingdom is well-guarded.

Prince Mabaning: I had vowed to find the Princess, even if my life is at stake, for she is the reason why I live.

Princess Anonen: Well, since no one can stop you, I advise you to disguise yourself as a Madem and pretend to be the messenger of Kilaten. If they recognize you, use this sword to render you invisible.

The prince continued his journey until he saw the vast space of Sagorongan-a-Ragat.

Scene 5: The Palace Tower in Sagorongan-a-Ragat

Mabaning disguised himself as a Madem. While walking all the way to the palace, Mabaning saw the sunken ship. The ship looks like his ship, the Kalipapa Da'ayaw. He asked the gypsies around.

Madem: My friend, what is that sunken ship?

Gypsies: That sunken ship is the ship of Prince Mabaning. King Dimasangkay is informed that the ship is in search of the missing Princess. The King made a quick response by firing cannons at those ships. The kingdom is now on guard for the possible attack of the people of Bembaran.

The prince is furious that he is about to explode, but he decides to set aside his mood and find the Princess in the palace tower of Sagorongan-a-Ragat

Gatekeeper: Who are you, and what's your purpose for coming here?

Madem: I am a messenger of Kilaten. I have something to ask the King, if our ties are still bound, for our King is worried.

The gatekeeper assists the Madem in front of the King.

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Madem: I am a messenger of Kilaten. I have something to ask: is our tie still bound for our King? We are not even informed about the sunken ship that dared to attack our beloved kingdom. We are also alarmed about the possible invasion of Bembaran, as expected.

King Dimasangkay: Kindly tell your King that the sunken ship is not a threat to our kingdom; that's why I never bothered to inform him. Also, tell him that yes, our ties are still bound, since the revenge of the people of Bembaran is inevitable and expected, given that they already know the Princess is here in Sagorongan-a-Ragat. Hence, I need the support of the King of Kilaten and his troops, as well as the people of the mountain, forest, and the highlanders, for the possible invasion.

Madem: Thank you, our beloved King. Before I go, may I request one thing? May I see the Princess beyond compare so I can brag in our kingdom that I see her with my own two eyes.

King Dimasangkay accepted his request. The King's guard accompanies the Madem. When the Madem is about to step on the stairs of the palace tower, he sees the Princess beyond compare. The Princess has recognized the Madem as Prince Mabaning, her sweetheart. She offered betel nut to the Madem as a friend, which she had never done before, but had offered it to King Dimasangkay. When the Madem received the betel-nut, he raised the magical sword given by the fairy princess of Kaugan and used it to command the fairy spirit to serve as wind in saving the Princess.

The news spread that the Madem is the Prince of Gadongan, Prince Mabaning Ndaw Rogong. The King is in dismay from being deceived. The two clashed together with their sharp Kampilan. The ship Rinayong has come, and the defense of the people of Bembaran has arrived. Mindalano sa Tonong supported the troops of King Dimasangkay, so the two groups clashed and drowned in battle.

Prince Minalang, related to both clans, has come and tried to stop the war. The number of Kadaraan's people waned, as the same fate befell the kingdom of Bembaran. Minalang commanded his emissaries to inform Minadalano sa Tonong that their King, Dimasangkay, is dead, and there's no sense in continuing the war anymore. So the people of Bembaran, under the leadership of Prince Mabaning Ndaw Rogong, began to feast for their victorious fight.